

1 **Highlights**

2 **Coupled EMAG-CFD-Thermal analysis of a novel Inductive Power Transfer system utilising**
3 **forced-liquid cooling with biodegradable dielectric fluid**

4 Nikolaos Rogkas,Alexandros Manios,Matthaios Pelekis,Emmanouil Karampasakis,Maria Fotopoulou,Vasilios Spi-
5 tas,Dimitrios Rakopoulos

- 6
- Assessment of the thermal aspects of a novel SST with IPT technology
 - Optimal design of the cooling system of the SST
 - Multi-faceted simulation strategy using coupled EMAG-CFD-FEA modeling
 - SST's thermal aspects parametric evaluation at various points of the cooling system
- 7
8
9

ORCID(s):

Coupled EMAG-CFD-Thermal analysis of a novel Inductive Power Transfer system utilising forced-liquid cooling with biodegradable dielectric fluid

Nikolaos Rogkas^{a,b,*}, Alexandros Manios^b, Matthaïos Pelekis^b, Emmanouil Karampasakis^b, Maria Fotopoulou^a, Vasilios Spitas^b and Dimitrios Rakopoulos^a

^aChemical Process and Energy Resources Institute, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, 52 Egialias Str., Maroussi, Athens, 15125, Greece

^bLaboratory of Machine Design and Dynamics, School of Mechanical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 9 Iroon Polytechniou, Athens, 15780 Zografou, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Solid State Transformer
Inductive Power Transfer
Cooling System
Heat Exchanger
Coupled EMAG-CFD-FEA Modeling

ABSTRACT

Solid state transformers (SSTs) are at the forefront of emerging technologies, enhancing distribution and transmission networks. These transformers facilitate the development of highly controllable and robust smart grids, seamlessly integrating renewable energy sources and accommodating connections for both alternating current and direct current components/lines at medium or low voltage levels. This research paper introduces an innovative SST incorporating the inductive power transfer (IPT) technology, currently under development within SSTAR, a Horizon Europe project. The IPT system is submerged in an ester-based, biodegradable dielectric fluid, providing effective cooling and insulation characteristics. The primary focus of this research is to highlight the guidelines for the optimal design of the forced liquid cooling system of the SST module. The analysis employs a multi-faceted simulation strategy to calculate the cooling aspects of the transformer, utilising the commercial software ANSYS. This involves 3D coupled Electromagnetic (EMAG) - Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations, as well as stand-alone CFD and thermal FEA simulations, ensuring robust validation of the obtained results. The findings underscore the efficiency and robustness of the proposed design, marking a significant step towards the realization of active and environmentally-friendly electrical networks.

1. Introduction

The ongoing energy transition has significantly affected the configuration of the electrical network, driven by the contemporary need for sustainable and environmental-friendly development of power systems. This, in turn, has prompted a fundamental reevaluation of how these systems should be designed and operated [1]. Over the past few decades, power systems, both in medium and low voltage levels, are populated with Renewable Energy Sources (RES) such as photovoltaics and wind farms, as well as energy storage systems, establishing a distributed, bidirectional and more advanced architecture [2]. While this approach enhances efficiency and viability, it necessitates a more complex infrastructure for proper operation [3]. This requirement has opened a research and development field focused on advanced transformers, converters, and protection schemes for power systems [4].

One of the most modern and promising solutions, drawing significant attention from both the research community and industry, is the Solid State Transformer (SST). Its primary objective is to replace conventional distribution transformers, i.e., the transformer that connects medium and low voltage levels, [5, 6, 7]. Unlike the conventional transformers, which are passive and only utilize Alternating Current (AC) at 50 or 60 Hz, the SST is power electronics device operating on medium and high frequencies, e.g. 50 kHz. It showcases advanced control capabilities, enhancing the robustness of power systems and inhibiting the propagation of disturbances between connected sides [8]. While its primary application lies in smart grids and microgrids [9, 10], it has found utility in the mobility sector, particularly in smart charging infrastructures [11].

However, while SST technology offers the potential for more controllable, scalable, and modular assemblies compared to conventional transformers, its widespread commercial adoption has not yet been established globally. This is due to its higher cost, increased complexity, and the fact that its design aspects are still in the process of

*Corresponding author

 n.rogkas@certh.gr (N. Rogkas)

59 being finalized [12, 13]. Given the relative novelty of this technology, there is currently no standardization in terms
60 of design, size, frequency of operation, or materials, prompting experts to actively work towards optimizing these
61 aspects in a cost-efficient manner [14]. For instance, SSTs exhibit variations, with some featuring a shell-type design
62 [15], while others incorporate the more state-of-the-art Inductive Power Transfer (IPT) system, which lacks a physical
63 connection between the primary and secondary sides [16, 17]. This innovation broadens its potential applications,
64 including contactless charging for electric vehicles [18].

65 One of the crucial factors influencing the operational lifetime, reliability, and loading capacity of SSTs is their
66 thermal characteristics, with excessive heat generated by electromagnetic losses being the primary cause of insulation
67 performance deterioration [19]. To counterbalance this, cooling systems can be integrated into the transformer. In
68 power networks, liquid-immersed power transformers, where dielectric liquid serves as both coolant and insulator, are
69 the prevailing type [20]. Ortiz et al. have also studied the aging impact on the cooling capacity of an ester oil [21], with
70 similar properties to the one used in this research.

71 The operational lifetime, reliability, and loading capacity of SSTs are significantly influenced by their thermal
72 characteristics, primarily due to the detrimental effects of excessive heat generated by electromagnetic losses [22, 23].
73 In power networks, a commonly employed type of transformer is the liquid-immersed power transformer, where
74 dielectric liquid serves a dual role as both coolant and insulator [20]. The temperature regulation of the biodegradable
75 dielectric fluid emerges as a crucial factor in the design process, contributing to the enhancement of voltage insulation.
76 This, in turn, increases the flexibility of SSTs and facilitates their seamless integration into high-voltage grids.

77 To address the issue of extensive heat fluxes, cooling systems can be seamlessly integrated into the transformer
78 design, with the usual choice being natural [24] or forced [25] liquid systems. Passive cooling systems utilize capillary
79 or gravitational forces to circulate the working fluid, while forced cooling systems are usually driven by a pump,
80 offering a significant advantage in terms of thermal removal capability. The optimal design of the cooling system is
81 essential to avoid operating faults and materials degradation due to thermal damage [26]. At the same time, the goal is
82 to streamline the transformer's dimensions, simplify its design, and optimize overall costs. The most efficient way of
83 cooling high-power transformers is to make use of forced liquid cooling [27]. This method takes advantage of a liquid's
84 higher heat density, capacity and thermal conductivity compared to air and enables the cooling of concentrated heat
85 sources in remote locations. Therefore, the physical design of the power electronics system is facilitated by enabling
86 the development of more compact systems with higher power density.

87 The evaluation of hot spot temperatures in the components of the SSTs poses another significant challenge
88 concerning their thermal aspects [28]. The prediction of the hot-spot temperature rise in the structural parts of
89 transformers relies heavily on the uneven distribution of electromagnetic losses, therefore causing non-uniform
90 temperature distribution and local hot-spots [29]. Liu et al. have developed a computational model with increased
91 efficiency to calculate the temperature increase of transformer windings submerged in oil [30]. Given that the location
92 of maximum loss density is typically where the hot spot is located, an accurate description of the stray loss distribution
93 is essential to compute the hot-spot temperature rise [20]. Therefore, accurate modeling of liquid flow and temperature
94 distributions within structural components is of utmost importance.

95 The approximation of thermal distribution in power transformers may be facilitated through the utilization of
96 numerical methods [31, 32, 33, 34, 35]. The electromagnetic (EMAG), thermal and flow aspects requirements of
97 transformers can be usually assessed using established software packages and appropriate finite element analyses
98 (FEA) and computational fluid dynamics (CFD). To achieve this, a magnetic-thermal coupling approach is mostly
99 adopted [36]. Specifically, the stray loss distribution obtained from the electromagnetic analysis serves as the boundary
100 conditions for the thermal/CFD analysis.

101 In recent years, numerous studies have been conducted to design and optimize SSTs in order to meet the increasing
102 demand for efficient and sustainable energy systems. A brief literature review is presented below. Beheshtaein et al. [37]
103 developed a hybrid liquid/air cooling system for an SST operating at 13 kV to 7.2 kV, 667 kW, 20 kHz, with the goal of
104 enhancing efficiency. Their work involved modeling the forced air-cooling and water-cooling system parts in ANSYS
105 Maxwell/Simplorer, ANSYS-Icepak, and ANSYS-Fluent, respectively. Jia et al. [20] investigated the temperature rise
106 and the mechanical properties of windings in an oil-immersed transformer and Stebel et al. [31] proposed an advanced
107 electromagnetic and thermo-fluid model of disk-type transformer and assessed its thermal characteristics using FEA.
108 Mogorovic et al. [38] developed an algorithm for the design of SSTs, including calculation of losses, magnetic energy
109 and hot-spot temperatures. According to the algorithm, a 100 kW, 10 kHz prototype was developed and tested, verifying
110 the theoretical design. Also, Roger et al. [39] presented a theoretical and experimental investigation on SSTs that
111 incorporate Grain Oriented Electrical Steel (GOES) and the possibility to design SSTs of several MW at a reasonable

cost, with a limited number of cells. The authors studied the core losses, the eddy currents and their effects on the temperatures developed in the SST.

While the designs and simulation approaches mentioned earlier primarily revolve around SSTs with interconnected primary and secondary cores, recent research has shown a growing interest in exploring the IPT technology due to its broader application potential [40]; however the main focus in these recent studies remains on their electronic aspects. For instance, Su et al. [41] presented a methodology to design SSTs with a specific emphasis on power electronics, which was evaluated through the manufacturing and testing of an IPT with an operating frequency equal to 200 kHz. Haque et al. [42] compared the performance of a 50 kW IPT, considering operation at both 22 kHz and 85 kHz with Si and SiC MOSFET. The system and its components were optimally designed for the two target frequencies, and consequent losses were evaluated through analytical, finite element, and circuit analysis. Tian et al. [43] proposed a coupled, semi-numerical model for the thermal analysis of a medium frequency transformer. Munoz-Cruzado Alba et al. [44] developed an SST in the context of TIGON, a Horizon 2020 project, with nominal power equal to 37.5 kW and switching frequency equal to 85 kHz. The purpose of this SST, which also incorporates an IPT system, is to facilitate the connection of AC/DC hybrid grids in medium and low voltage levels. Cervero et al. [45] developed a 50 kW SST prototype with an IPT system, operating at 2.2 kV with switching frequency equal to 29 kHz. The purpose of the prototype is to pave the way towards the enhancement of transmission lines and is part of the FST project. Finally, Dujic et al. [46] have developed an SST with IPT for the purpose of public transport charging infrastructures. The SST has nominal power equal to 54 kW, and operates at 1.5 kV with switching frequency equal to 1.5 kHz. Nevertheless, it's worth noting that the emphasis in these studies is predominantly on the electrical engineering aspects of SSTs, with comparatively less attention devoted to thermal considerations and, where applicable, the inclusion of a cooling system.

The purpose of this paper is to address this issue by developing a multi-faceted simulation strategy to evaluate the thermal aspects of a novel SST using the IPT technology, which is under development in the Horizon Europe SSTAR project [47]. The prototype to be manufactured is designed to operate at 1.5 kV / 0.4 kV with power equal to 50 kW and frequency equal to 50 kHz. The aim is to combine a number of such SSTs in order to reach higher voltage levels in an efficient, safe and sustainable way. For this purpose, the performance of the SST is enhanced through a ester-based, biodegradable dielectric fluid which is used both for insulation and cooling purposes. The proposed simulation strategy involves a 3D coupled EMAG-CFD model and stand-alone CFD and thermal FEA simulations, ensuring robust validation of the obtained results. In addition, an optimal design algorithm is proposed for the cooling system, taking into account the optimisation of its efficiency, effectiveness and pitch point operation. Finally, the developed simulation model is used to conduct parametric analyses regarding the effect of the cooling system on the SST hot spots. The findings underscore the efficiency and robustness of the proposed design, marking a significant step towards the realization of active and environmentally-friendly electrical networks.

2. SST Layout

Crucial factors influencing the functioning of such an SST configuration involve the structure of the coils, the space between them, the material of the core, and the design of the shields. This section discusses the modeling of the SST geometry and the configuration of the cooling system. The proposed layout for the cooling system consists of a mini pump, a heat exchanger and an aluminum tank. The tank contains the SST, which is submerged in the cooling medium. The circular process initiates with the oil exiting the tank at a warm temperature and low pressure. The working fluid then enters the mini pump, which delivers the liquid to the heat exchanger. The oil is cooled down in the heat exchanger by an ambient temperature forced air stream produced by a DC fan. Finally, the cold coolant enters the tank. For the recirculation to be enabled, it is important that the total pressure in the outlet of the tank is lower than the pressure in the inlet. As boundary conditions, a pressure inlet and a mass flow outlet setup has been selected, as it suitably describes the operational conditions of the system. As far as the heat exchanging mechanisms are concerned, conduction occurs from the direct contact between the windings, cores and shields, while the heat transfer between the dielectric fluid, the environment and the SST's components takes place with convection. Radiation emission also occurs due to the electromagnetic waves. A schematic of the total system, including the cooling system configuration and details about the geometry, the boundary conditions and the heat exchanging mechanisms that occur inside the structure is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of the total system, including the cooling system configuration and details about the geometry

2.1. SST Geometry

This subsection presents the geometrical modeling of the SST. In the context of SSTAR, a conceptual design of the SST module has been concluded, thus a simplified geometry intricately resembling this design is utilized for this research. The use of the simplified geometry relates also to the complexity of the simulations, given the development of an advanced coupled scheme (EMAG-CFD), thus contributing to the reduction of the required computational resources. The model's configuration is comprised by the dielectric fluid, magnetic cores, aluminum shields, and Litz windings, all immersed in the dielectric fluid. The Litz windings geometry has been constructed using a homogenized modeling approach, since it would be computationally inefficient to include a large number of small strands in the simulations. ANSYS Maxwell, offers the ability to analyze Litz wires model by accounting the number of strands and AC effects in the homogenized model. Within the fluid volume, there are inlet and outlet ports facilitating the circulation of the cooling medium. Upon selecting and validating the structures, the system's initial design phase concludes. Due to this simplified design, the topology of the system is maintained and the computational time is concurrently reduced.

2.2. SST Cooling system

The utilization of the proposed cooling system, as briefly illustrated in Figure 1 takes advantage of a liquid's higher heat density, capacity and thermal conductivity in comparison with air. This enables cooling concentrated heat sources in remote locations, therefore allowing more compact, higher power-density systems to be developed [48]. The biodegradable liquid used in this SST has dual purpose as it serves both as a dielectric fluid and a cooling medium. Regarding the system's design, a criterion that was taken into consideration is that the temperature of the cooling oil is meant to be held under a threshold of 100 °C.

The pump and heat exchanger selection for the cooling setup of a wireless SST significantly impact the system's performance and reliability. Cooling systems like this one, which are dependent on direct oil-forced flow, necessitate a pumping system between the oil tank and the heat exchanger to achieve a high flow rate of the insulating oil [49]. Multiple factors must be considered during the pump selection process. In order to effectively cool the transformer, the pump needs to meet the necessary flow rate and counteract pressure drops in the pumping network caused by losses in the heat exchanger and piping. Since the flow rate is proportional to the pressure drop, it is significant to note that

186 higher flow rates could potentially create inlet pressure decrease in the tank. Due to the significant pressure drop in
 187 commercially available heat exchangers at the scale of this application, it is assessed that the flow rates should range
 188 between 0.25-1 kg/s, considering a flow rate of 0.5 kg/s as the nominal value for the purposes of this research. The
 189 chosen pump should match the necessary flow rates and pressure head while operating at its peak efficiency, ensuring
 190 minimal energy consumption. The final criterion that determines the selection of a pump is its compatibility with the
 191 operating liquid as well as with the temperatures and pressures encountered in the system.

192 Power electronic cooling applications require heat exchangers to transfer heat from the cooling liquid to another
 193 medium such as air in this instance. For this application an air-oil heat exchanger is used due to their high thermal
 194 performance and high-pressure resistance [50]. Before the choice of a compact heat exchanger, a lot of parameters
 195 need to be considered. The thermal load of the system is examined as well as whether the heat exchanger can withhold
 196 it. Another factor to be considered in the choice of a heat exchanger is its ability to transfer heat from one liquid to
 197 another. It has been assessed that a heat transfer capability of at least 1000 W/°C is sufficient to fulfil the system's
 198 needs and examine a vast range of output temperatures for the hot oil stream. Essentially, a heat exchanger with a lower
 199 capability may be suitable for this application. However, for the purposes of this research, a larger heat exchanger
 200 was assumed in order to allow the examination of a greater temperature range. The selected capability for the heat
 201 exchanger is related to commercially available heat exchangers and their ability to operate under certain mass flow
 202 rates, while simultaneously providing enough power to alter the fluid's temperature to the desired value and maintain
 203 the pressure levels. Furthermore, the function of the whole cooling system is greatly influenced by the effectiveness of
 204 the exchanger [51]. Consequently, the operating point of the radiator is thoroughly examined and optimized considering
 205 variables such as efficiency and pinch point, apart from the effectiveness.

206 In order to initiate the optimisation process of the heat exchanger, the temperature at the outlet of the SST tank
 207 is required. This has been calculated by conducting a CFD simulation (zero velocity) under no-cooling conditions,
 208 therefore allowing for the capturing of the temperature field of the SST. Then, the calculated outlet temperature of the
 209 SST is utilized as an inlet temperature of the heat exchanger and is kept constant during the optimisation process. This
 210 simulation serves the purpose of examining the maximum thermal load of the system and therefore assesses the
 211 operation of the heat exchanger in extreme conditions. The temperature used in this optimization approach is 80 °C,
 212 obtained at the outlet of the tank.

213 Pinch analysis has been implemented on the heat exchanger, in order to estimate the range of temperatures that the
 214 cooling oil can reach, after the exchange process. In order for the operation to take place, the high-end temperature
 215 of both the hot and cold streams must be below the pinch point temperature, where the hot and cold composite
 216 curves indicate the minimum temperature difference [52]. For the purposes of this analysis, the pinch point is assumed
 217 equivalent to the theoretical pinch point, where the two curves intersect. If the temperature is higher than the pinch
 218 point, then the exchanger operates at its heating section, whereas if the temperature is lower than the pinch point it
 219 operates at the cooling section [53], which serves the purposes of this application. The results of the pinch analysis
 220 conclude that in order to remain in the cooling operation area of the exchanger the ester oil is able to exit the heat
 221 exchanger at a temperature range spanning from 38-75 °C. The composite curves for the cold and hot stream for
 222 variable outlet temperatures are presented in Figure 2.

223 The optimization algorithm has been implemented by utilising an objective function, comprised by curve-fitted data
 224 regarding three optimization parameters multiplied by variable weighting factors. The format of the objective function
 225 that is the subject of minimization in the current algorithm is presented in Equation 1, where the functions f_1 , f_2 , f_3
 226 are generated by curve fitting the relations created by the parametric temperature data obtained by the pinch analysis
 227 and represent the pinch point, efficiency and effectiveness respectively.

$$f(T_{out_{hot}}) = w_1 f_1(T_{out_{hot}}) + w_2 f_2(T_{out_{hot}}) + w_3 f_3(T_{out_{hot}}) \quad (1)$$

228 The optimization parameters that were selected for this research are the effectiveness and efficiency of the heat
 229 exchanger, as well as the minimization of the pinch point. An estimation of the effectiveness and efficiency of the
 230 exchanger is conducted using a combination of the Log Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD) and the Effectiveness-
 231 NTU method (e-NTU) [54, 55]. Aiming to minimise the objective function, all optimization variables have been
 232 expressed through their relation with a single variable, the outlet temperature of the hot stream. The optimization
 233 algorithm's goal is to minimize the constrained nonlinear function and achieve a certain tolerance ($<10^{-6}$) to obtain
 234 optimal solutions. Figure 3 demonstrates the optimization regarding the operation of the heat exchanger.

Figure 2: Thermal pinch diagram for 43 °C outlet temperature from the heat exchanger. The theoretical pinch point is located inside the green circle.

Figure 3: Optimization process of the heat exchanger

235 3. Materials

236 For this study, the material assignments are induced by the modeling of the system, the proposed simulation strategy
 237 and the specifications relative to the project. The materials used for the coupled simulations and their electromagnetic
 238 properties are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Material assignments & electromagnetic properties

Properties	Windings	Cores	Shields
Material	Copper	Ferrite	Aluminum
ϵ_r	1	12	1
μ_r	0.9999	$0.069 \ln(H) + 0.031$ [56]	1.000021
σ (S/m)	5.8×10^7	0.15	3.8×10^7 (°C))
Core loss model	-	Power Ferrite	-
ρ (kg/m ³)	8933	4600	2689
Wire Type	Round	-	-
Strand Number	1650 (HV) 330 (LV)	-	-
d_w (mm)	0.16	-	-

The same materials are also used in the thermal/CFD simulations, thus their thermal properties are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Thermal material properties

Properties	Windings	Cores	Shields
k (W/m°C)	400	4	237.5
c_p (J/kgK)	385	750	951
α (1/°C)	1.77×10^{-5}	10^{-5}	2.33×10^{-5}
Surface Finish	Polished	Cast machine cut	Anodized

For the cooling system of the SST a biodegradable, ester-based oil was experimentally tested by Novamont S.p.A., a partner of the Consortium, to obtain the electromagnetic and thermal properties. The temperature dependent properties are presented in Figure 4, while some properties that are considered constant are described in Table 3.

Table 3: Constant properties of the dielectric/cooling liquid

a (1/°C)	ϵ_r	$\tan(\delta)$
0.00071	3.1	0.06

Relative to the properties of Table 3 the thermal diffusivity of the ester-based oil can be calculated by the formula described in Equation 2.

$$D = K / \rho c_p \quad (2)$$

Figure 4: Temperature-dependent properties for the cooling oil measured by Novamont S.p.A. a) Density, b) Specific heat, c) Thermal conductivity, d) Dynamic viscosity. The points indicate the measured data while the lines refer to the fitted curves.

249 4. Numerical Methodology

250 This application requires a multi-faceted simulation strategy to obtain robust results. The strategy proposed in
 251 this research includes the use of different modules of the ANSYS software, which are used to verify the operation
 252 of the cooling system of the SST. The first computational approach of the simulation strategy illustrated in Figure
 253 5 regards an EMAG-CFD two-way coupling of the system's functionality using the ANSYS Maxwell and ANSYS
 254 Icepak modules. The second objective of the strategy is to perform a CFD analysis including specified heat generation
 255 and heat transfer coefficients linked to the structures according to the resulting power losses from EMAG, in order to
 256 obtain a satisfactory approximation of the temperature and flow fields by one-way coupling the two models. The third
 257 objective concerns a thermal simulation, which models the generated heat via a convection model, thus generating a
 258 temperature field in ANSYS Thermal. The estimations regarding the magnitude of heat generation originate from the
 259 initial power loss calculations in ANSYS Maxwell, while the ambient conditions derive from the CFD simulations,
 260 thus coupling the thermal model to both EMAG and CFD. The entirety of the proposed simulation strategy and the
 261 methodology concerning the simulations are depicted in the flowchart of Figure 5.

Figure 5: Proposed simulation strategies. The EMAG simulation conducted in ANSYS Maxwell is 2-way coupled with the CFD simulation on ANSYS Icepak. Similarly, the CFD simulation in ANSYS Fluent is one-way coupled with the EMAG simulation, from which the data for the power losses and heat transfer coefficients are obtained. The thermal simulation is one-way coupled with both the EMAG and CFD simulation in order to emulate the power losses as well as the temperature of the flow surrounding the SST's components.

4.1. Governing Equations

The governing equations which describe the simulations differ per simulation strategy, depending on each software utilized. This section presents a comprehensive analysis of the equations used internally in the softwares during the research [57, 58, 59, 60].

4.1.1. ANSYS Maxwell

Before setting up the model to be simulated on ANSYS Maxwell the field solver is determined. For the purposes of this model the eddy current solver is utilized. The source of the electromagnetic field in this case are the sinusoidal AC currents in the conductors, and are used by the field simulator to compute electromagnetic fields in the frequency domain. The eddy current field simulator solves for the magnetic field \mathbf{H} and the magnetic scalar potential Ω . As a result, the magnetic flux density \mathbf{B} and the current density are automatically calculated. The \mathbf{T} - Ω formulation is used by the 3D eddy current solver, which assumes that all electromagnetic fields pulsate with the same frequency. Maxwell is thus used in order to calculate the initial phase angles and magnitudes. During this process, all objects are considered stationary. Equation 3 gives the magnetic field strength in the non-conducting regions, where the vector \mathbf{H}_p represents the externally applied magnetic field, and $\nabla\Omega$ concerns the magnetic field produced by the eddy currents.

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_p + \nabla\Omega \quad (3)$$

Equation 4 is used in regions where eddy current calculation has been set up. Using edge elements, this equation computes electric vector potential, represented by \mathbf{T} .

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_p + \nabla\Omega + \mathbf{T} \quad (4)$$

278 The solver uses the formula in Equation 5 in order to solve for the magnetic field (H). A differentiation is made
 279 between non-conducting regions and conducting regions where eddy current occurs. In the former, H is calculated
 280 from the magnetic scalar potential given by Equation 6. In the latter regions, H is computed from source currents
 281 and applied in magnetic fields. In the following equations, μ represents the permeability of the material. The direct
 282 solver is used only in locations where the magnetic potential cannot be used, since directly solving for H requires large
 283 computational resources.

$$\nabla \left(\frac{1}{\sigma + j\omega\epsilon} \nabla H \right) = -j\omega\mu H \quad (5)$$

$$\nabla(\mu\nabla\phi) = 0 \quad (6)$$

284 Taking this into consideration the relationship between the magnetic flux density B and the magnetic field H is
 285 described in Equation 7.

$$\begin{bmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{bmatrix} = [\mu] \begin{bmatrix} H_x \\ H_y \\ H_z \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

286 The same methodology may be applied for all anisotropic properties of each material such as relative permittivity.
 287 As far as the core loss models of the simulation are concerned, the two cases are described through a discrete expression
 288 in each one. For the power ferrite core loss model, it is given by Equation 8, described by the Steinmetz formula [61]:

$$p = C_m f^{x_{St}} B_{max}^{y_{St}} \quad (8)$$

289 Where C_m , x_{St} and y_{St} are material parameters. The parameter C_m is a constant value determined by experiment,
 290 f is the frequency and B_{max} expresses the maximum amplitude of the flux density. The values for these constants have
 291 been thoroughly examined in [62], whose study provides valuable graphs and tables expressing these parameters.

292 4.1.2. ANSYS Icepak

293 In order to compute the CFD model, the Navier-Stokes equations are solved, as shown in Equations 9, 10 for
 294 transport of mass and momentum. Similarly, when calculating laminar flow with heat transfer, equation 11 is used.
 295 When the flow is turbulent additional equations must be added. The mass conservation equation is described by
 296 Equation 9, which considers both compressible and incompressible flows.

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \nabla(\rho\mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (9)$$

297 The momentum conservation equation is presented in Equation 10. This describes the transport of momentum in
 298 an inertial (non-accelerating) reference frame, where p is the static pressure, $\rho\mathbf{g}$ is the gravitational body force and the
 299 vector \mathbf{F} contains various source terms that may arise due to resistances, sources etc.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho\mathbf{u}) + \nabla(\rho\mathbf{u}\mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla(\mu[(\nabla\mathbf{u} + \nabla\mathbf{u}^T) - \frac{2}{3}\nabla\mathbf{u}I]) + \rho\mathbf{g} + \mathbf{F} \quad (10)$$

300 Furthermore, the energy conservation equation is presented in Equation 11 as a relation of the sensible enthalpy
 301 h , molecular conductivity k , the conductivity due to turbulent transport and the source term S_h , which includes any
 302 volumetric heat sources that have been defined.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \int_{T_{ref}}^T c_p dT) + \nabla \cdot (\rho\mathbf{u} \int_{T_{ref}}^T c_p dT) = \nabla \cdot [(k + \frac{c_p\mu_t}{Pr_t})\nabla T] + S_h \quad (11)$$

303 In conducting solid regions, Icepak solves the simple conduction equation provided in Equation 12, where ρ is the
 304 density, k the conductivity, T the temperature and S_h the volumetric heat source.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho h) = \nabla(k\nabla T) + S_h \quad (12)$$

In this case, additional transport equations are solved due to the turbulent nature of the flow. The $k-\omega$ SST (Shear Stress Transport) model is used to simulate a low Reynolds number turbulence model. While a low Reynolds number is a characteristic of a laminar flow, local turbulent effects may occur [63]. The transport equations related to the specific turbulence model for the intermittency are presented in Equation 13, while Equation 14 illustrates the function for the transition onset criteria.

$$\frac{\partial(\rho\gamma)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho U_j \gamma)}{\partial x_j} = P_{\gamma_1} - E_{\gamma_1} + P_{\gamma_2} - E_{\gamma_2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\gamma} \right) \frac{\partial \gamma}{\partial x_j} \right] \quad (13)$$

Where $P_{\gamma_1}, E_{\gamma_1}, P_{\gamma_2}, E_{\gamma_2}$ are the transition sources linked to the turbulence model.

$$F_{\text{onset}} = \max \left\{ \min \left[\max \left(\frac{Re_v}{2193 Re_c}, \left(\frac{Re_v}{2193 Re_c} \right)^4 \right), 2.0 \right] - \max \left[\left(1 - \left(\frac{R_t}{25} \right)^3 \right), 0 \right], 0 \right\} \quad (14)$$

The transition model interacts with the SST turbulence model by modifying the k -equation, as demonstrated in Equation 15.

$$\frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho k u_i)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\Gamma_k \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + G_k - Y_k + S_k \quad (15)$$

The above transition model formulation is thoroughly described by Menter et al. [64]. Γ_k is a function of molecular and eddy viscosities and Y_k and G_k are the destruction and production terms of the $k - \omega$ SST model.

4.1.3. ANSYS Fluent

The basic fluid flow is described by the same equations (Navier-Stokes) that are used in ANSYS Icepak (Equations 9, 10). In such low velocities the compressibility effects are insignificant, thus the flow is considered incompressible. ANSYS Fluent solves the energy equation in the following form (Equation 16) in order to include heat transfer aspects in the simulation.

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \left(\rho \left(e + \frac{v^2}{2} \right) \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\rho v \left(h + \frac{v^2}{2} \right) \right) = \nabla \cdot \left(k_{\text{eff}} \nabla T - \sum_j h_j \mathbf{J}_j + \tau_{\text{eff}} \mathbf{v} \right) + S_h \quad (16)$$

In Equation 16, k_{eff} is the effective conductivity and is equivalent to $k + k_t$ as it is illustrated in Equation 11, with k_t representing the turbulent thermal conductivity. \mathbf{J}_j is the diffusion flux of species j . The first three terms on the right-hand side of Equation 16 represent energy transfer due to conduction, species diffusion and viscous dissipation respectively. The enthalpy h is defined in Equation 17 for incompressible materials similarly to the definition for ideal gases, with the main difference being the inclusion of contribution from pressure work.

$$h = \sum_j Y_j h_j + \frac{p}{\rho} \quad (17)$$

In Equation 17, Y_j is the mass fraction of species j and h_j is the sensible heat of species, meaning that it is a part of enthalpy that includes only changes in the enthalpy due to specific heat as demonstrated in Equation 11. Additionally, ANSYS Fluent also solves Equations 13-15 when calculating the SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model.

4.1.4. ANSYS Thermal

To model the heat generated by conduction and convection inside the structure, the solver uses the first law of thermodynamics, which is related to the conservation of thermal energy, and specializes it to a differential control volume as stated in Equation 18.

$$\rho c_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \{u\}^T \nabla T \right) + \nabla \cdot \{\mathbf{q}\} = \ddot{q} \quad (18)$$

In this equation, ρ denotes the density, c_p is the specific heat, T is the temperature, t is time, \mathbf{q} is the heat flux vector, \dot{q} is the heat generation rate per unit volume. Equation 19 defines the analytical value for \mathbf{u} .

$$\mathbf{u} = \begin{pmatrix} u_x \\ u_y \\ u_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

To relate the heat flux vector to the thermal gradients, Fourier's law is used in Equation 20.

$$\{q\} = - \begin{bmatrix} K_{xx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \nabla T \quad (20)$$

By processing Equation 10 and then expanding the resulting equation Equation 21 is used.

$$\rho c_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + v_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v_y \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} + v_z \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) = \ddot{q} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (K_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (K_y \frac{\partial T}{\partial y}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (K_z \frac{\partial T}{\partial z}) \quad (21)$$

By employing these equations, it is implied that all effects take place within the global Cartesian system. Moreover, certain default boundary conditions are taken into account, presuming they cover the entirety of the element. Equation 22 concerns specified temperature, Equation 23 specified heat flows and Equation 24 specified convection all acting over a surface S.

$$T = T^* \quad (22)$$

$$(q)^T n = -q^* \quad (23)$$

$$q^T n = \alpha(T_s - T_B) \quad (24)$$

In the above equations, T^* is the specified temperature, $\{\mathbf{n}\}$ is the unit outward normal vector, q^* is the specified heat flow, α is the film coefficient. T_B is the bulk temperature of the adjacent fluid, which is considered equal to the free-stream temperature when dealing with a fluid flowing past a solid surface. T_s is the temperature at the surface of the model.

4.2. Computational Model Setup

This section includes descriptive information regarding the computational model setup for each of the presented simulations. Namely, the boundary conditions are analysed and explained along with the mesh generation and independence study.

ANSYS Maxwell uses tetrahedral elements to define the mesh, implementing refinement methods such as length-based and skin depth-based to obtain the necessary mesh density. For the purposes of this study both refinement methods are used, depending on the meshing requirements of each structure. The length-based method is used for the cores and shields, while the skin depth based refinement is preferred for the windings and a layered mesh is created. A structured hexahedral mesh has been created in ANSYS Fluent and Mechanical. Figure 6 represents the main geometric dimensions of the SST along with the computational meshes for the EMAG, CFD and thermal simulations respectively. The dielectric fluid mesh has been refined around the transformer structures.

The computational mesh for each of the simulation strategies has been studied concerning the independence of the temperature of the components with respect to the mesh density. The independence study for ANSYS Maxwell and Icepak has been conducted at the primary cores displaying the trend of the core losses and temperatures respectively along a rectangular path as depicted in Figure 7. The fine mesh, comprised by a total of 1.1 million elements has been evaluated accurate for the purposes of this simulation.

363 Regarding ANSYS Fluent, the grid is studied in a cross sectional mid-plane along the x, y axes of the fluid domain.
364 Figure 8 contains the graphical data regarding the independence of the grid for ANSYS Fluent. The deviations between
365 the finer grids have been deemed insignificant, therefore a fine mesh with 1.15 million elements has been implemented.

Figure 6: Main geometric dimensions of the SST and computational mesh. **a.** Geometry of the SST and main dimensions, **b.** EMAG mesh, isometric view, **c.** Fluent mesh, isometric view, **d.** Icepak mesh, section view, **e.** Fluent mesh, section view, **f.** Thermal mesh, isometric half-section view.

Figure 7: Mesh independence study for ANSYS Maxwell and Icepak. **a.** Core loss distribution along the rectangular path, **b.** Temperature distribution along the same path.

Figure 8: Mesh independence study regarding the flow characteristics of the fluid domain in the region between the SST structures for the case of 43 °C and 0.5 kg/s in ANSYS Fluent. **a.** Temperature values, **b.** Pressure values, **c.** Velocity values.

366 The thermal mesh deviations occurring by the refinement of the mesh are displayed in Table 4. In total, four
 367 increasing mesh densities have been examined, and it is assessed that a total number of approximately 630000
 368 hexahedral elements is sufficiently accurate as the deviation percentage comparing to a 910000 element grid is below
 369 0.5 %.

Table 4: Thermal mesh independence.

Mesh density	Coarse	Medium	Fine	Very fine
Total # of elements	221860	438310	630730	913430
Max T (°C)	56.514	56.508	56.509	56.509
Min T (°C)	49.125	49.141	49.132	49.161
Mean T (°C)	52.543	52.548	52.544	52.539
Max Dev. (%)	-	1.68	0.855	0.418

370

371 **4.2.1. Electromagnetic simulation**

372 The time-varying external magnetic fields are ignored, in order to reduce the required computational resources.
373 Regarding the eddy current solution, natural boundaries have been inserted on the interface between the structures,
374 where the magnetic field is continuous. Niemann outer boundaries have been implemented, where the magnetic field
375 is tangential to the boundary and the flux may not cross it. The surfaces of the dielectric fluid are modelled as insulating
376 boundaries mainly with the purpose to distinct the coils from the cores.

377 The excitations relative to this model are set as current type in order to be used in conjunction with the material
378 conductivity and define the current through a solid conductor. Coil terminals are defined in the windings and the
379 respective current excitations are specified. The direction of the applied current is always normal to the respective
380 surfaces.

381 **4.2.2. CFD simulations**

382 The boundary conditions and model setup for the ANSYS Icepak & Fluent simulations remain consistent between
383 the two packages, in order to achieve the desired consistency between the two softwares and accurately validate the
384 results. At the inlet of the tank, due to the design of the piping network, the pressure is known, therefore a pressure inlet
385 is designated. Respectively, the mass flow at the outlet of the tank is constant and a mass flow outlet is set. An inverted
386 set of boundary conditions (mass flow inlet-pressure outlet) has also been examined, but the deviations in the results
387 were deemed insignificant. ANSYS Icepak is directly coupled to the electromagnetic simulation, therefore the mesh
388 is directly imported from ANSYS Maxwell, while for ANSYS Fluent an independent mesh study has been conducted.
389 The thermal load conditions, are also derived from the EMAG simulation and are determined by the power loss results
390 obtained for each component. In ANSYS Fluent, similar boundary conditions have been set, with the main difference
391 being that the power loss sources are approximated in this instance.

392 A discrete simulation is examined solely on ANSYS Icepak regarding an operating scenario of the SST without
393 the cooling system, which facilitates the study regarding the heat exchanger. The thermal loading scenario neglecting
394 the operation of the cooling system, is described by a steady state (only temperature) solution type and the equilibrium
395 state of the system is assumed. This model takes into consideration solely the energy equations (11-12,16), since the
396 fluid has zero velocity inside the tank. For this simulation no convection is set to be performed between the dielectric
397 fluid and the solid bodies, hence the resulting temperature rise is the maximum. The walls have been designated to
398 allow heat flow outside the set domain and the effect of radiation through the materials' surfaces is also considered
399 significant.

400 For the case describing the effect of the cooling system on the hot-spot temperature of the SST all structures are
401 assigned with electromagnetic losses, thus coupling the power losses obtained by Maxwell to the CFD simulation.
402 The inlet surface of the inlet pipe is modelled as an opening flow port with a pressure inlet equal with the total
403 pressure calculated from the piping network. The inlet temperature is assigned equal to the outlet temperature of the
404 heat exchanger according to the optimization approach. The same principles apply to the outlet pipe, which has been
405 designated as an opening out-flow port. The external surfaces of both the inlet and outlet ports are stationary walls,
406 with a thickness of 3mm and wall temperature equal to the ambient. Furthermore, the tank's walls have been designated
407 to perform convection with the environment, considering an assumed heat transfer coefficient. All material's surfaces
408 have been stipulated to emit radiation at an ambient temperature of 22 °C. Specifically, in ANSYS Fluent the radiation
409 effects have been disregarded, inside the tank and only radiation emitted from the tank to the environment is considered.

410 **4.2.3. Thermal simulation**

411 The calculation of the temperature distribution along each component of the SST is conducted with the use of
412 a thermal simulation using the environment of ANSYS Mechanical, in order to emulate the heat transfer conditions
413 (convection, radiation) as illustrated in Figure 1. The model is built by generating a hexahedral mesh to reduce the
414 computational time and obtain a structured grid. Each component has been assigned an internal heat generation, which
415 approximates the effect of the power losses on the components. Additionally, the heat transfer coefficient and the
416 ambient temperature has been set for each object. The ambient temperature serves as a medium to emulate the flow
417 surrounding the structure, and is thus approximated based on the free stream temperature calculated from the CFD
418 simulations.

4.3. Operating Parameters

The boundary conditions and operating parameters for the EMAG and CFD simulations are summarized in Table 5. The thermal simulation is comprised by a magnitude of internal heat generation for each component, relevant to the power loss deducted from EMAG. Furthermore, the heat transfer between the components is modelled as convection in all instances. Therefore, a heat transfer coefficient is assumed and the ambient temperature surrounding each object is approximated via ANSYS Fluent to emulate the temperature of the fluid domain around the respective structures. The inserted values regarding the heat generation distribution among the components and the set temperatures are in accordance with the other simulation softwares and are presented in Table 6.

Table 5: Excitations, operating parameters and boundary conditions

	EMAG		CFD	
	HVW	LVW	BCs & Operating Parameters	
Excitations	Coil Terminal - Stranded		Inlet type	Pressure inlet
Conductors	20	5	p_{in} (bar)	1.9
Direction	Out	Into	Outlet type	Mass Flow outlet
Winding Type	Current		\dot{m}_{out} (kg/s)	0.5
I (A)	31.25	118.75	Wall Type	Stationary
θ (°)	0	45	Model	Laminar
T_{amb} (°C)			22	

Table 6: Excitations, operating parameters and boundary conditions applied in ANSYS Fluent and Mechanical

	HVW	LVW	PC	SC	PS	SS
\ddot{q} (W/mm^3)	0.002	0.001	0.00045	0.0003	0	0
α (W/mm^2K)	6.85×10^{-4}	7.03×10^{-4}	1.68×10^{-4}	1.83×10^{-4}	$1.016.85 \times 10^{-4}$	1.03×10^{-4}
T_{amb} (°C)	53	51	46	44	43	43

5. Results and Discussion

In this section, the results regarding the multi-faceted simulation strategy are demonstrated. Specifically, the power losses obtained from EMAG are presented and lead to the calculation of the temperature distribution in the bodies, using CFD and thermal simulations. The characteristics of the flow inside the fluid domain are assessed using ANSYS Fluent. The CFD simulations are additionally conducted for parametric input data, obtained from the piping network and the optimization process of the heat exchanger.

5.1. Parametric Input Data

The operation of the SST is examined under variable operating conditions, namely mass flow rate and inlet temperature. The temperature of the flow at the inlet of the tank is highly dependent on the heat exchanger, therefore the optimization approach provides valuable insights regarding the range of feasible temperatures in relation with the temperature at the inlet of the exchanger. A simulation of the SST has been conducted in ANSYS Icepak, without accounting for the use of the cooling system in order to make an educated approximation regarding the flow temperature at the outlet of the tank and consequently the inlet of the exchanger. The resulting temperature, related to the boundary condition of the optimization, is assessed to be 80 °C.

The required performance of the heat exchanger is specified taking into consideration all the parameters mentioned beforehand. Regarding the mass flow rate, it is constrained by the limitations of the operating pressure inside the network. Namely, as the mass flow rate increases, the pressure drop inside the heat exchanger increases exponentially, therefore the maximum mass flow rate that the proposed system can withhold is 1 kg/s. A parameter range of 0.5-1 kg/s is hence examined for the SST. The optimization of the exchanger, is conducted for a constant flow of 0.5 kg/s. It is also assumed that the air flow in the heat exchanger is facilitated by a DC fan, operating at an ambient temperature of 22 °C

Figure 9: Distribution of the outlet temperature of the hot stream as a function of the weighting factors combinations. The weighting factors w_1 , w_2 and w_3 represent the pinch point temperature, efficiency and effectiveness respectively according to Equation 1

and producing an airflow of 10 m/s. The relation between the pinch point temperature, the effectiveness and efficiency is evaluated and the optimization process is executed producing the results depicted in Figure 9. A selection of optimum outlet temperatures for the heat exchanger has been conducted factoring that all criteria must be evaluated. Scoping to maximum efficiency a temperature of 43 °C has been selected, while the optimization results regarding effectiveness and pinch point indicate that the optimum temperatures are 53 °C and 38 °C respectively. These temperatures are later going to be utilized as free stream temperatures in CFD and thermal simulations.

5.2. Maxwell-Icepak 2-way coupling

The results regarding the electromagnetic field and the fluid dynamics and energy from the coupled simulation are presented in Figure 10. The total losses in the primary and secondary cores are calculated to be approximately 0.5 kW, while the ohmic losses in the windings are 0.25 kW. It is evident, that the maximum losses, accounting for both ohmic and core losses, occur at the location of the windings. As expected, the power losses in the LV components are significantly lower in comparison with the HV. It is assessed that the dielectric losses are in the order of 0.02 kW and are considered negligible.

The same principal also applies to the temperature fields. The temperature appears to increase in the regions where the power loss density is highest. The temperature levels indicate that the SST operates within the acceptable temperature limits, as the maximum temperature inside the tank does not exceed 100 °C, rather it is calculated to be 53.9 °C. The representing temperature fields for the fluid domain, also indicate promising results, since the temperature increases as the flow circulates from the inlet to the outlet of the tank due to the absorption of thermal energy produced by the structural components.

As illustrated in Figure 10, the total power losses in the cores and windings is estimated to be in the order of 1 kW. The temperature distribution along the respective components is expected according to the power loss distributions calculated in ANSYS Maxwell. In the regions where the power losses exhibit higher values, according to EMAG, the temperature appears accordingly increased. The temperature in the structure's section parallel to the flow is decreased, due to the effect of the cooling oil. The total temperature of the SST's components and cooling liquid does not exceed 100 °C, as per the specifications of the project.

474 As revealed by these contours, major temperature increases occur at the copper windings within the transformer due to
 475 to inherent ohmic losses. Similarly, the core losses within the ferrite cores have a similar effect on these components'
 476 temperatures. These temperature escalations propagate throughout the system, finally reaching the shields of the
 477 assembly and imprinting an increased temperature field on them. The thermal analysis also highlights the expected
 478 temperature elevation in the working medium during operation when contrasted with its cool initial inflow temperature.

479 The CFD simulation conducted in ANSYS Fluent has provided valuable insights regarding the biodegradable fluid
 480 flow conditions inside the tank. Namely, as illustrated in Figure 11 the pressure remains at an almost constant level
 481 inside the tank, but areas of slight pressure drop or increase are exhibited. The main area of concern in that matter is
 482 the swift pressure increase in the tank walls near the outlet leading some streamlines to produce backflow. The velocity
 483 contours and vectors, showcase that the flow remains nearly steady, exhibiting velocity magnitudes near zero in the
 484 regions between the tank walls and the SST. The flow, mainly passes in the region between the primary and secondary
 485 components, where the velocity magnitude is increased to over 0.8 m/s.

Figure 10: Results concerning the electromagnetic field simulated in ANSYS Maxwell, fluid dynamics and energy obtain by the coupled CFD simulation in ANSYS Icepak. The colorbar boundaries of the contours are shared between the primary and secondary components. This synchronization facilitates a direct visual comparison between the two, allowing for a clear demonstration of their relationship. **a.** Core loss distribution, **b.** Ohmic loss distribution, **c.** Temperature distribution in the cores, **d.** Temperature distribution in the windings, **e.** Temperature distribution in the shields, **f.** Temperature contour for the entire fluid domain and tank.

Figure 11: Flow conditions inside the tank. **a.** Pressure contour. Local pressure augmentation near the region of the outlet walls, **b.** Velocity contour. The pressure increments at the vertical walls near outlet pipe cause backflow to occur, as the flow collides with the tank walls, **c.** Temperature contour. The stream temperature maintains its levels near to the free stream temperature, affected only in the area near the transformer's components and close to the walls of the tank, where convection with the environment takes place.

5.3. Model Validation

The robustness of the 2 way coupled simulation model is validated by further examination of the temperature fields using CFD and FEA. This part of the analysis has been conducted for a free stream temperature of 43 °C as the optimal temperature, which maximizes the efficiency of the heat exchanger. It is assessed that the temperature levels have been validated by the three simulation approaches and the results have a mean deviation error at the order of 10%. Figure 12 showcases a comprehensive visualization of these deviations through a composite display of error bars. The resultant bars cumulatively depict the outcomes from all simulation strategies, providing a holistic view of the data in each point.

The positions of the hot spots near the windings showcase slight differences across the modules due to the distinct physics employed by each solver and the use of boundary conditions. These positional variations, combined with the steep temperature increments in the winding circumferential regions, result in both increased and reduced localized relative errors in the distribution, as demonstrated in Figure 12. These variations offset each other, hence reflecting the true mean error values as depicted in Table 7.

The findings also reveal that along the cooling oil direction (X), the Thermal simulation leads to comparatively larger deviations. This discrepancy occurs since this module accounts for static conditions, thereby neglecting the flow dynamics of the working medium. Consequently, it produces higher and more uniform temperature values near the core hot spots which lead to estimations of the maximum temperatures in these regions. This deviation is not as pronounced in the vertical (Z) direction, where fluid flow occurs within a more confined region. In this direction's surrounding areas, while flow persists, its velocity is also significantly lower, diminishing its impact on the overall outcome. Furthermore, based on the temperatures obtained by the CFD simulations, a thermal simulation, being less computationally demanding, can sufficiently approximate the temperature thresholds in a heat transfer model as such, with the mean deviation results reaching an order as low as 5%.

Equally small deviations appear in the comparison between the two CFD models conducted in ANSYS Icepak and Fluent respectively. The error in this case can be attributed to the modeling of the heat generation inside the structures

509 being uniform. In the regions where the effect of the cooling flow is increased, the temperature distribution is closer to
 510 the results obtained in Icepak, while in the areas where the flow has a smaller effect, Fluent approximates the results
 511 from the thermal simulation. Hence, despite the few observed localized disparities in the outputs, the average errors
 512 remain sufficiently small (in the order of 10%).

Figure 12: Temperature distribution through the cores using three simulation strategies. **a.** Temperature fluctuation in paths created along the z and x axis respectively. The bars illustrating the deviations between the simulation are presented vertically stacked and each color represents the origin of the error, **b.** Contours regarding the primary and secondary cores for all simulation strategies. The cross paths where the temperatures have been plotted are illustrated in the Icepak contours.

Table 7: Relative error data

	X Direction		Z Direction	
	Icepak - Thermal	Icepak - Fluent	Icepak - Thermal	Icepak - Fluent
Mean PC ϵ (%)	16.25	9.97	9.70	10.06
Mean SC ϵ (%)	9.27	3.55	4.58	3.84
Mean ϵ (%)	9.76		7.04	
Max ϵ (%)	24.37		15.12	

513

514 Table 8 demonstrates a comparison between similar works conducted in literature on the topic of SSTs. The novelty
 515 of this research is further reinforced due to the coupled temperature and CFD analysis conducted, since it addresses
 516 the thermal aspects of SSTs with IPT technology at a high frequency.

Table 8: Comparison of different studies

Literature	Max T (°C)	f (kHz)	E (kW)	Cooling system	Type
Mogorovic et al. [38]	~125	10	100	Natural convective air cooling	Shell
Beheshtaein et al. [37]	~64	20	667	Forced air and water	Shell
Cervero et al. [45]	-	29	50	Not included	IPT
Munoz-Cruzado Alba et al. [44]	-	85	37.5	Not included	SST
Dujic et al. [46]	-	1.5	54	Not included	PETT
Haque et al. [42]	-	22, 85	50	Not included	IPT
This paper	~58	50	50	Forced cooling	IPT

518 5.4. Parametric Analysis Results

519 This section presents the results related to the parametric simulations of the SST, examining variable temperature
 520 and mass flow conditions. Variable temperatures have been examined in order to evaluate different thermal loading
 521 scenarios, including the prospect of a lower-thermal capacity heat exchanger. As the thermal load, hence temperature,
 522 is increased, the effect of the components' power losses decreases. As a result, the temperature difference between the
 523 primary and secondary structures also slightly decreases. In all instances, the maximum temperature does not exceed
 524 100 °, therefore all presented cases describe viable operation points of the SST. The parametric temperature results are
 525 presented in Figure 13.

526 Furthermore, the effect of the mass flow rate on the temperature distribution is evaluated. The mass flow rate
 527 magnitude is constrained by the pressure drop of the network (piping, heat exchanger etc.), thus placing the maximum
 528 value included in this calculation at 1 kg/s. As expected, an increased mass flow rate contributes to a significant
 529 temperature drop in the cores, converging to the temperature of the free stream. While a higher mass flow rate reinforces
 530 the effect of the cooling system, it is essential to note that a detailed design of the cooling network is needed in order
 531 to achieve higher velocities and maintain the pressure levels. The respective results are presented in Figure 14.

Figure 13: Temperature distribution along the cores' x and z axis for parametric free stream temperatures of the cooling oil at a reference mass flow rate of 0.5 kg/s. Results along the a. X direction, b. Z direction.

Figure 14: Temperature distribution along the cores' x and z axis for parametric cooling oil mass flow rates at a reference temperature of 43 °C. Results along the **a.** X direction, **b.** Z direction.

6. Conclusions

This study has provided valuable insights concerning the operation of the SST and the surrounding network. Specifically, the SST has been evaluated in variable temperature and mass flow conditions through different simulation strategies implementing EMAG, CFD and thermal analysis using ANSYS software packages. Namely the electromagnetic fields and losses have been assessed through ANSYS Maxwell, CFD simulations have been conducted in ANSYS Fluent and Icepak, while the thermal simulation has been set up in ANSYS Mechanical. The purpose of implementing three simulation strategies was to provide robust and validated results from a number of different sources, with small deviations occurring between them.

Additionally, a heat exchanger and pump system have been examined to facilitate the operation of the system. The heat exchanger has been optimized regarding the outlet temperature of the stream taking into account variables such as efficiency, effectiveness and pinch point temperature. The results obtained from the pinch analysis provide guidelines regarding the range of feasible temperature boundary conditions for the CFD and thermal simulations, while the optimization approach produces optimal temperature cases regarding maximum efficiency, effectiveness and operation proximal to the pinch point. A feasible outlet temperature range, assuming that the heat transfer capability of the heat exchanger is 1000 W/°C is 38-75 °C. The optimization algorithm has provided decisive results regarding the optimal output temperature, which may range from 38-63 °C, depending on the prioritization of the optimization metrics. The temperatures of the cooling oil stream that were simulated for the purposes of this research are 43, 53, 60 °C.

The electromagnetic simulations have provided information regarding the losses within the cores and windings of the structure. The total losses occurring in the SST's components are in the order of 1 kW and are distributed unevenly in the structures' volume. Deriving from the magnetic field and losses, temperature distributions have been constructed by simulating the effect of the cooling system under different conditions in ANSYS Icepak. The temperature distributions validate the desired threshold of maintaining the temperature of the structures and fluid domain below 100 °C. Namely, the maximum temperature developed inside the SST is 58 °C. The temperature field results have been cross-validated by the implementation of further CFD and thermal analysis using different software and the resulting mean deviation has been deemed satisfactory, since it remains in the order of 10 %. The biodegradable fluid flow conditions such as total pressure and oil velocity inside the tank have also been examined using ANSYS Fluent and it is assessed that for the examined velocity and pressure range the velocity contour forms a jet formulation between the structures, as expected from the initial consideration of the system topology and diameter changes. It is also observed that minimal

561 pressure drop occurs inside the tank, which can be mainly attributed to velocity reduction, hence dynamic pressure
562 drop, caused by the forced oil flow inside the structures.

563 A comparison of the results presented in this paper with similar researches, indicates that a lower hot-spot
564 temperature is achieved, especially when taking into account the high frequency of operation. The obtained results
565 contribute to the development of SSTs as an innovative replacement of the conventional distribution transformers and
566 a deeper understanding regarding the thermal aspects of such power systems is attained.

567 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

568 **Nikolaos Rogkas:** Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal Analysis, Inves-
569 tigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review Editing, Visualization. **Alexandros Manios:**
570 Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. **Matthaios**
571 **Pelekis:** Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization.
572 **Emmanouil Karampasakis:** Methodology, Software, Visualization. **Maria Fotopoulou:** Investigation, Writing -
573 Original Draft. **Vasilios Spitas:** Supervision. **Dimitrios Rakopoulos:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Project admin-
574 istration, Supervision.

575 **Acknowledgement**

576 The authors would like to thank Ms. Angela Sagliano from Novamont S.p.A. for providing the experimental data
577 of the ester-based dielectric fluid.

578 **Funding Source**

579 This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme [Project: SSTAR,
580 Grand Agreement: 101069702]

581 **Nomenclature**

Symbol	Description
c_p	Specific heat
B	Magnetic flux density
C_m, x_{St}, y_{St}	Steinmetz constants
d	Diameter
D	Thermal diffusivity
E	Energy / Power
f	Frequency
G_k	Production term of k- ω SST model
f_1, f_2, f_3	Fit curve functions for heat exchanger optimization
\mathbf{F}	Source terms vector
\mathbf{g}	Gravity acceleration constant
h	Enthalpy
\mathbf{H}	Magnetic field
\mathbf{J}	Diffusion flux
k	Thermal conductivity
I	Current
\mathbf{n}	Normal vector
p	Pressure
$P_{\gamma_1}, P_{\gamma_2}, E_{\gamma_1}, E_{\gamma_2}$	Transition sources
\mathbf{q}	Heat flux vector
\dot{q}	Heat generation per unit volume
\ddot{q}	Heat generation rate per unit volume
Re	Reynold's number
S_h	Source term (volumetric heat source)
t	Time
T	Temperature
\mathbf{T}	Electric vector potential
\mathbf{u}	Velocity vector
ν	Dynamic viscosity
w_1, w_2, w_3	Weighting factors for heat exchanger optimization
x, y, z	Cartesian system directions
Y	Mass fraction
Y_k	Destruction term of k- ω SST model

583 **Subscripts**

Subscript	Description
amb	Ambient
B	Bulk
eff	Effective
hot	Referring to the hot stream of the heat exchanger
in	Referring to an inlet
j	Species j
out	Referring to an outlet
s	Surface of the model
t	Turbulence
$wire$	Referring to the wire
x, y, z	Cartesian system directions

585 **Abbreviations**

Abbreviation	Full Form
AC	Alternating Current
BC	Boundary conditions
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DC	Direct Current
EMAG	Electromagnetics
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
GOES	Grain Oriented Electrical Steel
HVW	High Voltage Winding
IPT	Inductive Power Transfer
k- ω SST	k- ω Shear Stress Transport
LMTD	Log Mean Temperature Difference
LVW	Low Voltage Winding
max	Maximum value
min	Minimum value
NTU	Number of Transfer Units
PC	Primary Core
PETT	Power Electronic Traction Transformer
PC	Primary Core
PS	Primary Shield
SC	Secondary Core
SS	Secondary Shield
SST	Solid State Transformer

587 **Greek Letters**

Greek Letter	Description
α	Heat transfer coefficient
ϵ	Error
Γ_k	Function of molecular viscosity and eddy viscosity
$\tan(\delta)$	Dielectric loss tangent
ϵ_r	Relative permittivity
θ	Phase
μ_r	Relative permeability
ρ	Mass density
σ	Bulk conductivity
$\nabla\Omega$	Magnetic field by eddy currents

589 **References**

590 [1] Nelson S. Chipangamate and Glen T. Nwaila. Assessment of challenges and strategies for driving energy transitions in emerging markets: A
591 socio-technological systems perspective. *Energy Geoscience*, 5:100257, 4 2024.

592 [2] Dimitris Al. Katsaprakakis, Antonia Proka, Dimitris Zafirakis, Markos Damasiotis, Panos Kotsampopoulos, Nikos Hatziaargyriou, Eirini
593 Dakanali, George Arnaoutakis, and Dimitrios Xevgenos. Greek islands’ energy transition: From lighthouse projects to the emergence of
594 energy communities. *Energies*, 15:5996, 8 2022.

595 [3] Maria Fotopoulou, Dimitrios Rakopoulos, Dimitrios Trigkas, Fotis Stergiopoulos, Orestis Blanas, and Spyros Voutetakis. State of the art of
596 low and medium voltage direct current (dc) microgrids. *Energies*, 14:5595, 9 2021.

597 [4] Mohammad Sazib Mollik, Mahammad A. Hannan, Md Subbir Reza, Muhamad Safwan Abd Rahman, Molla Shahadat Hossain Lipu, Pin Jern
598 Ker, Muhamad Mansor, and Kashem M. Muttaqi. The advancement of solid-state transformer technology and its operation and control with
599 power grids: A review. *Electronics 2022, Vol. 11, Page 2648*, 11:2648, 8 2022.

600 [5] Jonas Emanuel Huber and Johann Walter Kolar. Solid-state transformers: On the origins and evolution of key concepts. *IEEE Industrial
601 Electronics Magazine*, 10:19–28, 9 2016.

- [6] Dillip K. Mishra, Mojtaba J. Ghadi, Li Li, Md. Jahangir Hossain, Jiangfeng Zhang, Prakash K. Ray, and Asit Mohanty. A review on solid-state transformer: A breakthrough technology for future smart distribution grids. *International Journal of Electrical Power Energy Systems*, 133:107255, 12 2021.
- [7] Hamed Shadfar, Mehrdad, Ghorbani Pashakolaei, Asghar, Akbari Foroud, and Asghar Akbari Foroud. Solid-state transformers: An overview of the concept, topology, and its applications in the smart grid. *International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems*, 31:e12996, 9 2021.
- [8] Eneko Unamuno and Jon Andoni Barrera. Hybrid ac/dc microgrids—part i: Review and classification of topologies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 52:1251–1259, 12 2015.
- [9] Dillip K. Mishra, Mojtaba J. Ghadi, Li Li, Md. Jahangir Hossain, Jiangfeng Zhang, Prakash K. Ray, and Asit Mohanty. A review on solid-state transformer: A breakthrough technology for future smart distribution grids. *International Journal of Electrical Power Energy Systems*, 133:107255, 2021.
- [10] Xu She, Alex Q. Huang, and Rolando Burgos. Review of solid-state transformer technologies and their application in power distribution systems. *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, 1(3):186–198, 2013.
- [11] Seyedamin Valesaravi, Abdelali El Aroudi, and Luis Martínez-Salamero. Review of solid-state transformer applications on electric vehicle dc ultra-fast charging station. *Energies*, 15(15), 2022.
- [12] Pramod Apte, Siqi Lin, Lukas Fräger, and Jens Friebe. Design considerations for a 50 kw dual bridge series resonant dc/dc converter with wide-input voltage range for solid-state transformers. In *2021 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, pages 1164–1170, 2021.
- [13] Hao Chen, Anish Prasai, Rohit Moghe, Kireeti Chintakrinda, and Deepak Divan. A 50-kva three-phase solid-state transformer based on the minimal topology: Dyna-c. *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, 31(12):8126–8137, 2016.
- [14] Jayrajsinh Solanki and Kalpesh Chudasama. Concepts, configurations and challenges of solid state transformer: A review. *Recent Advances in Electrical Electronic Engineering (Formerly Recent Patents on Electrical Electronic Engineering)*, 15, 07 2022.
- [15] Mahammad A. Hannan, Pin Jern Ker, Molla S. Hossain Lipu, Zhen Hang Choi, M. Safwan Abd. Rahman, Kashem M. Muttaqi, and Frede Blaabjerg. State of the art of solid-state transformers: Advanced topologies, implementation issues, recent progress and improvements. *IEEE Access*, 8:19113–19132, 2020.
- [16] Chenyang Xia, Limin Liu, Yuling Liu, and Zhixun Ma. Inductive power transfer system for tail-free household appliances in smart home system. *IET Power Electronics*, 12, 05 2019.
- [17] Christoph Degen. Inductive coupling for wireless power transfer and near-field communication. *EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking*, 2021, 05 2021.
- [18] David Cervero, Maria Fotopoulou, Jesús Muñoz-Cruzado, Dimitrios Rakopoulos, Fotis Stergiopoulos, Nikos Nikolopoulos, Spyros Voutetakis, and José Francisco Sanz. Solid state transformers: A critical review of projects with relevant prototypes and demonstrators. *Electronics*, 12:931, 2 2023.
- [19] Vitaly A. Yatshevsky. Hydrodynamics and heat transfer in cooling channels of oil-filled power transformers with multicoil windings. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 63(1):347–353, 2014.
- [20] Xiaoyu Jia, Mei Lin, Shiwei Su, Qiuwang Wang, and Jian Yang. Numerical study on temperature rise and mechanical properties of winding in oil-immersed transformer. *Energy*, 239, 1 2022.
- [21] A. Ortiz, F. Delgado, Félix Ortiz, Inmaculada Fernández, and Agustín Santisteban. The aging impact on the cooling capacity of a natural ester used in power transformers. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 144:797–803, 2018.
- [22] Waluyo Waluyo, Siti Saodah, and Rohana. Investigation of transformer losses and temperature rise. *EEA - Electrotehnica, Electronica, Automatica*, 66:37–44, 04 2018.
- [23] M.A. Taghikhani. Power transformer winding thermal analysis considering load conditions and type of oil. *International Journal of Material and Mechanical Engineering*, 1(6), 2012.
- [24] Xiang Zhang, Muhammad Daghrah, Zhongdong Wang, and Qiang Liu. Flow and temperature distributions in a disc type winding-part ii: Natural cooling modes. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 165:114616, 1 2020.
- [25] Muhammad Daghrah, Xiang Zhang, Zhongdong Wang, Qiang Liu, Paul Jarman, and David Walker. Flow and temperature distributions in a disc type winding-part i: Forced and directed cooling modes. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 165:114653, 1 2020.
- [26] Leyla Raeisian, Hamid Niazmand, Ehsan Ebrahimnia-Bajestan, and Peter Werle. Thermal management of a distribution transformer: An optimization study of the cooling system using cfd and response surface methodology. *International Journal of Electrical Power Energy Systems*, 104:443–455, 1 2019.
- [27] Young Joo Kim, Myunggeun Jeong, Yong Gap Park, and Man Yeong Ha. A numerical study of the effect of a hybrid cooling system on the cooling performance of a large power transformer. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 136:275–286, 5 2018.
- [28] D. P. Rommel, D. Di Maio, and T. Tinga. Transformer hot spot temperature prediction based on basic operator information. *International Journal of Electrical Power Energy Systems*, 124:106340, 1 2021.
- [29] Xiaoling Yu, Youbo Tan, Haotian Wang, Xiaolin Wang, Ying Zang, and Penghong Guo. Thermal analysis and optimization on a transformer winding based on non-uniform loss distribution. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 226:120296, 2023.
- [30] Gang Liu, Wanjun Hu, Shiyuan Hao, Chenglong Gao, Yunpeng Liu, Weige Wu, and Lin Li. A fast computational method for internal temperature field in oil-immersed power transformers. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 236:121558, 2024.
- [31] Michal Stebel, Krzysztof Kubiczek, Gustavo Rios Rodriguez, Michal Palacz, Luciano Garelli, Bartłomiej Melka, Michal Haida, Jakub Bodys, Andrzej J. Nowak, Pawel Lasek, Mariusz Stepień, Francisco Pessolani, Mauro Amadei, Daniel Granata, Mario Storti, and Jacek Smolka. Thermal analysis of 8.5 mva disk-type power transformer cooled by biodegradable ester oil working in onan mode by using advanced emag-cfd-cfd coupling. *International Journal of Electrical Power Energy Systems*, 136:107737, 3 2022.
- [32] Ole H.H. Meyer, Karl Yngve Lervåg, and Åsmund Ervik. A multiscale porous-resolved methodology for efficient simulation of heat and fluid transport in complex geometries, with application to electric power transformers. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 183:116133, 2021.

- [33] F. Torriano, P. Picher, and M. Chaaban. Numerical investigation of 3d flow and thermal effects in a disc-type transformer winding. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 40:121–131, 2012.
- [34] Jon Gastellurrutia, Juan Carlos Ramos, Gorka S. Larraona, Alejandro Rivas, Josu Izagirre, and Luis del Río. Numerical modelling of natural convection of oil inside distribution transformers. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 31(4):493–505, 2011.
- [35] Mehdi Allahbakhshi and Milad Akbari. Heat analysis of the power transformer bushings using the finite element method. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 100:714–720, 2016.
- [36] Zhen Wang, Kai Xu, and Yufeng Du. Temperature rise calculation of magnetic core considering the temperature effect of magnetic properties in an electrical steel sheet. *Symmetry* 2022, Vol. 14, Page 2315, 14:2315, 11 2022.
- [37] Siavash Beheshtaein, Ahmad Alshafei, Garry Jean-Pierre, Necmi Altin, Mahydy Khayamy, Robert Cuzner, and Adel Nasiri. An optimal design of a hybrid liquid/air cooling system for high power, medium frequency, and medium voltage solid-state transformer. pages 1–8. IEEE, 6 2021.
- [38] Marko Mgorovic and Drazen Dujic. 100 kw, 10 khz medium-frequency transformer design optimization and experimental verification. *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, 34:1696–1708, 2 2019.
- [39] Daniel Roger, Ewa Napieralska, Krzysztof Komez, and Piotr Napieralski. Design of high-power solid-state transformers with grain-oriented electrical steel cores. *Electronics*, 11:2398, 7 2022.
- [40] Kyung-Hee Han, Byung-Song Lee, and Soo-Hyun Baek. The design evaluation of inductive power-transformer for personal rapid transit by measuring impedance. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 103:07E928, 4 2008.
- [41] Qian Su, Xin Liu, Yan Li, Xiaosong Wang, Zhiqiang Wang, and Yu Liu. A graphical design methodology based on ideal gyrator and transformer for compensation topology with load-independent output in inductive power transfer system. *Electronics*, 10:575, 3 2021.
- [42] Moinul Shahidul Haque, Mostak Mohammad, Jason L. Pries, and Seungdeog Choi. Comparison of 22 khz and 85 khz 50 kw wireless charging system using si and sic switches for electric vehicle. pages 192–198. IEEE, 10 2018.
- [43] Haonan Tian, Zhongbao Wei, Sriram Vaisambhayana, Madasamy Thevar, Anshuman Tripathi, and Philip Kjær. A coupled, semi-numerical model for thermal analysis of medium frequency transformer. *Energies*, 12:328, 1 2019.
- [44] Jesus Munoz-Cruzado Alba, David Cervero, Oscar Izquierdo, Eduardo Garcia-Martinez, Ruben Gonzalez-Fernandez, Jose Ignacio Abad, and Antonio Rojas. Solid-state transformers for dc-ac hybrid grids: a case study of tigon project. In *PCIM Europe 2023; International Exhibition and Conference for Power Electronics, Intelligent Motion, Renewable Energy and Energy Management*, pages 1–9, 2023.
- [45] Jesús Muñoz-Cruzado Alba José Francisco Sanz Osorio Juan Manuel Perié Buil David Cervero García, Eduardo García-Martínez and Andrea Soto Rodríguez. Solid-state transformers for high voltage applications: Fst project use case. In *2022 7th International Advanced Research Workshop on Transformers (ARWtr)*, 2022.
- [46] Drazen Dujic, Chuanhong Zhao, Akos Mester, Juergen K. Steinke, Michael Weiss, Silvia Lewdeni-Schmid, Toufann Chaudhuri, and Philippe Stefanutti. Power electronic traction transformer-low voltage prototype. *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, 28(12):5522–5534, 2013.
- [47] Sstar-innovative hv solid-state transformer for maximizing renewable energy penetration in energy distribution and transmission systems. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069702>. Accessed: 2023-12-10.
- [48] Andrei Blinov, Dmitri Vinnikov, and T. Lehtla. Cooling methods for high-power electronic systems. *Scientific Journal of Riga Technical University. Power and Electrical Engineering*, 29:79–86, 10 2011.
- [49] Min gu Kim, Sang Moon Cho, and Joong-Kyoung Kim. Prediction and evaluation of the cooling performance of radiators used in oil-filled power transformer applications with non-direct and direct-oil-forced flow. *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, 44:392–397, 2013.
- [50] Yinlong Liu, Guoqiang Xu, Yanchen Fu, Jie Wen, and Haoran Huang. Thermal dynamic and failure research on an air-fuel heat exchanger for aero-engine cooling. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, 42:102715, 2023.
- [51] Tom Kowalski and A. Radmehr. Thermal analysis of an electronics enclosure: Coupling flow network modeling (fnm) and computational fluid dynamics (cfD). pages 60 – 67, 02 2000.
- [52] Chapter 10 pinch point analysis. In Alexandre C. Dimian, editor, *Integrated Design and Simulation of Chemical Processes*, volume 13 of *Computer Aided Chemical Engineering*, pages 393–434. Elsevier, 2003.
- [53] Yi Zhu, Adetoyese Olajire Oyedun, Maojian Wang, and Chi Wai Hui. Simultaneous optimization of a heat integrated coal gasification process. *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, 98:136–146, 2015.
- [54] Ahmad Fakheri. Efficiency analysis of heat exchangers and heat exchanger networks. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 76:99–104, 2014.
- [55] Ahmad Fakheri. Heat exchanger efficiency. *Journal of Heat Transfer*, 129, 09 2007.
- [56] Applying fairchild power switch (fpstm) fsbh-series to standby auxiliary power supply 1. 2009.
- [57] ANSYS®. *Maxwell Help*. ANSYS, Inc., January 2023. Release 2023R1.
- [58] ANSYS®. *Icepak Help*. ANSYS, Inc., January 2023. Release 2023R1.
- [59] ANSYS®. *Ansys Fluent Theory Guide*. ANSYS, Inc., January 2023. Release 2023R1.
- [60] ANSYS®. *ANSYS Mechanical ADPL Theory Reference*. ANSYS, Inc., January 2023. Release 2023R1.
- [61] J. Reinert, A. Brockmeyer, and Rik De Doncker. Calculation of losses in ferro- and ferrimagnetic materials based on the modified steinmetz equation. *Industry Applications, IEEE Transactions on*, 37:1055 – 1061, 08 2001.
- [62] Kalina Detka and Krzysztof Górecki. Modelling the power losses in the ferromagnetic materials. *Materials Science-Poland*, 35, 01 2017.
- [63] Alex Skillen, Alistair Revell, Hector Iacovides, and Wei Wu. Numerical prediction of local hot-spot phenomena in transformer windings. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 36:96–105, 2012.
- [64] Florian Menter, RB Langtry, S. Likki, Y. Suzen, P. Huang, and S Völker. A correlation-based transition model using local variables—part i: Model formulation. *ASME J. Turbomach*, 128, 07 2006.